

Genetic diversity among upland rice varieties from India and Bangladesh

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Isozyme analysis is a simple and powerful tool to examine genetic diversity of rice varieties for neutral markers. Rice germplasm was classified into six groups based on allelic associations across 15 isozyme loci. Understanding the pattern of variation existing among varieties grown in a given ecosystem is important for breeders and could help to optimize the choice of parents for hybridization.

We analyzed 64 upland rice varieties from India and Bangladesh (see table), traditional and improved, for their isozyme variation at 14 loci—*Adh1*, *Amp1*, *Amp2*, *Amp3*, *Amp4*, *Cat1*, *Est1*, *Est2*, *Est5*, *Est9*, *Icd1*, *Pgi1*, *Pgi2*, and *Sdh1*. For each variety, we analyzed 10 coleoptiles that allowed us to assess within-sample diversity.

Five among the 14 tested loci were monomorphic (*Amp4*, *Est5*, *Icd1*, *Adh1*, *Cat1*). The 64 varieties were classified using an algorithm based on the alleles present at 5 loci (*Pgi1*, *Pgi2*, *Amp3*, *Amp2*, *Amp1*). Thirty-five belonged to the indica group (mostly improved varieties) and 22 belonged to the aus group (partly traditional, partly improved varieties) as defined in the classification established by Glaszmann (1987). This grouping reflects the strategy developed by Indian upland rice breeders who favor recombina-

tions between indica and aus types in their selection programs. The aus group brings good adaptation to the aerobic soil conditions prevailing in the upland ecosystem, whereas the indica group is used for its yield potential.

Several samples, notably among the traditional varieties, were mixtures of different types for one or several loci. This phenomenon is frequently encountered in traditional varieties and can be observed even in varieties that are phenotypically homogeneous, but induces some difficulties in the classification, notably when the samples are mixtures for the classifying loci. Five varieties could not be assigned to a varietal group (noted with “?” in the table).

The classification in groups is meaningful mostly for the traditional varieties. Because of the recombinations occurring in improved varieties,

Classification of upland rice varieties from India and Bangladesh into isozyme groups.^a

Variety	Type	Country of origin	Isozyme group ^b	Within-sample diversity ^c	Variety	Type	Country of origin	Isozyme group ^b	Within-sample diversity ^c
Akashi	IMP	IND	1	M (3)	Rasi	IMP	IND	1	H
Annada	IMP	IND	1	M (2)	RP2220-111-84-20	IMP	IND	1	H
Aus196	TRAD	BGD	2	M (1)	RP2235-35-40-5	IMP	IND	1	H
Aus257	TRAD	BGD	2	M (2)	RR13-51	IMP	IND	1*	H
Aus454	TRAD	BGD	2	M (1)	RR137-83-5	IMP	IND	2	H
Bala	IMP	IND	1	M (1)	RR139-1	IMP	IND	1	H
Birsadhan 101	IMP	IND	1	M (2)	RR149-177	IMP	IND	1	H
Birsadhan 102	IMP	IND	2	H	RR151-3	IMP	IND	1	H
Black Gora	TRAD	IND	?	M (4)	RR151-85	IMP	IND	2	H
BR20	IMP	BGD	1	M (2)	RR151-91	IMP	IND	2	M (1)
BR4290-3-3-5	IMP	BGD	1+6	H	RR159-90	IMP	IND	2	M (1)
Brown Gora	TRAD	IND	2	M (2)	RR165-1160	IMP	IND	1	M (1)
Cauvery	IMP	IND	1	H	RR166-645	IMP	IND	1	H
CH45	TRAD	IND	1	H	RR167-982	IMP	IND	1*	M (1)
Charka Gora	TRAD	IND	2	M (1)	RR174-1	IMP	IND	2	M (1)
CO 13	IMP	IND	1+6	H	RR180-1	IMP	IND	1*	H
CR143-2-2	IMP	IND	2	M (1)	RR19-2	IMP	IND	1*	M (1)
Dehula	TRAD	IND	?	M (7)	RR2-6	IMP	IND	1*	M (1)
Dular	TRAD	IND	2	M (1)	RR20-5	IMP	IND	2	M (2)
Dumai	TRAD	IND	1*	H	RR227-8	IMP	IND	1	M (1)
Hira	IMP	IND	1	H	RR235-64	IMP	IND	1*	M (1)
Jonga	TRAD	IND	2	H	RR50-128	IMP	IND	1	H
Kalakeri	TRAD	IND	2	H	RR50-3	IMP	IND	1	M (1)
Kalinga III	IMP	IND	1	M (1)	RR51-1	IMP	IND	1	H
Kalyani 2	IMP	IND	1	H	RR6-1	IMP	IND	2	M (2)
Karhni	TRAD	IND	2	M (1)	Saita	TRAD	IND	2	M (4)
Lalnakanda 41	TRAD	IND	2	H	Sattari	IMP	IND	?	M (6)
Laloo 14	TRAD	IND	1	H	Sathi 34-36	TRAD	IND	?	M (7)
N22	TRAD	IND	2	H	Surjamukhi	TRAD	IND	2	H
Nagpur 26	TRAD	IND	1	H	Vanapraba	IMP	IND	1	H
Neela	IMP	IND	1	M (1)	Vandana	IMP	IND	1	H
Prasanna	IMP	IND	1	H	VHC 1253	TRAD	IND	?	M (4)

^a TRAD = traditional variety, IMP = improved variety (includes selection from or mutant of a traditional variety); IND = India; BGD = Bangladesh, H = homogeneous sample; M = mixture of types. ^b 1 = indica; 1* = close to indica; 2 = aus; 1+6 = recombination of indica and japonica alleles, ? = unclassified. ^c Number in parentheses indicates the number of loci with several alleles. The classification of varietal groups is based on the most frequent allele.

Breeding methods

Performance of exotic (IRRI) and locally developed cytoplasmic male sterile lines at Kapurthala, Punjab, India

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Stability of a cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line is of the utmost importance for hybrid rice to be commercially useful. In this study, 20 IRRI CMS lines (IR66707A carrying *Oryza perennis* cytoplasm and all others carrying wild abortive [WA] cytoplasm imparting male sterility) and 13 locally developed CMS lines (all WA-derived) were evaluated for male sterility, days to 50% flowering, plant height, anther color, and grain type at PAU in Kapurthala during the 1996 kharif (wet season). The seeds of CMS lines were produced by hand pollination on a paired plant basis. Each CMS line was planted in paired rows of 12 plants. Spacing between rows and among plants was 20 cm. During flowering, anthers of 5-10 spikelets from two tillers of each plant were squashed and pollen grains were stained with 1% IKI solution and observations for sterile (unstained) pollens were made from five or six microscopic fields. Two panicles of each plant were also bagged before anthesis to study their spikelet fertility at maturity. Based on the degree of male sterility, a CMS line was termed as completely sterile, highly sterile, sterile, partially sterile, or partially fertile.

Of the locally developed CMS lines, PbCMS 1A, 2A, 3A, 4A, 8A, 10A, 11A, 12A, and 13A were completely sterile; 7A, highly sterile; and 5A, 6A, and 9A, partially sterile. Among the IRRI-bred CMS lines, 11 were completely sterile, three highly sterile, and the remaining six partially sterile to partially fertile (see table).

some samples presented an allelic combination that did not allow a clear-cut classification (CO 13 and BR4290-3-3-5 assigned to group 1+6). From allelic variation at the polymorphic loci, we established a dendrogram clustering 62 of the varieties (Sattari and Sathi 34-36 excluded) according to their genetic similarity based on Euclidean distances

(see figure). This tree shows the same clear-cut differentiation into two groups corresponding roughly to the two varietal groups. The aus group appears less diverse than the indica group. The dendrogram can be used as a tool to help breeders choose parents on the basis of their genetic distance to maximize potential genetic progress. ■